

METHOD OF SYNERGETIC SYNTHESIS FOR HIERARCHICAL INSPECTION AND CONTROL OF INDUSTRIAL ROBOTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20813449>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 18th June 2026

Accepted: 20th June 2026

Online: 22nd June 2026

KEYWORDS

industrial robot, hierarchical control, synergetic synthesis, expert regulator, neural-network identifier, stability, diagnostics, intelligent robotic system

ABSTRACT

This thesis develops a synergetic synthesis approach for hierarchical inspection and control of industrial robots. In the work, the upper strategic level, tactical coordination level, and actuator control at the executive level are linked through a single synergetic macrovariable. The proposed model is aimed at increasing the motion accuracy of an industrial manipulator, its resistance to external disturbances, and its real-time diagnostic capability. The thesis mathematically substantiates the elements of synergetic control, expert evaluation, and neural-network identification within a hierarchical inspection system.

Introduction

In modern manufacturing, industrial robots are regarded not simply as execution mechanisms, but as intelligent robotic systems capable of sensing, analysis, decision-making, and checking the performed motion. In such systems, perceiving the external environment, processing data, making independent decisions, and accurately performing specified tasks are essential requirements. Therefore, the use of only a classical PID controller or rigid programmed control in industrial robots is not sufficient; the robot must continuously evaluate its own state, load, trajectory deviation, and the technical condition of its actuators.

The relevance of the problem lies in the fact that, in flexible manufacturing systems, robots handle parts of different masses, obstacles appear in the working zone, the inertia moment of drives changes, and noise occurs in sensor information. Under such conditions, centralized control cannot recalculate all processes at the microsecond level. Therefore, hierarchical inspection of the robot is necessary: the upper level defines the task and safety constraints, the tactical level evaluates the motion trajectory and the state of the environment, and the executive level generates the control signal corresponding to the current state of the drives.

The purpose of the study is to develop a synergetic synthesis model that corresponds to the hierarchical inspection system of an industrial robot. To achieve this aim, the following tasks were performed: representing robot dynamics in vector-matrix form, selecting a macrovariable, specifying the law of convergence to the invariant manifold, introducing diagnostic residual signals, and evaluating stability based on the Lyapunov criterion.

Materials and Methods

The research material consisted of general theoretical approaches to the principles of constructing intelligent robotic systems, the knowledge base of expert systems, the identification capabilities of neural networks, and hierarchical control levels. The methodological basis is synergetic control theory. In this approach, the control object is brought to a special invariant manifold in the state space. If the vector of generalized coordinates for the robot manipulator is $q \in \mathbb{R}^n$, its dynamics is written as follows:

$$M(q)\ddot{q} + C(q, \dot{q})\dot{q} + G(q) + F\dot{q} = \tau + d(t). \quad (1)$$

Here, $M(q)$ is the inertia matrix, $C(q, \dot{q})$ is the matrix of Coriolis and centrifugal terms, $G(q)$ is the vector of gravitational moments, $F\dot{q}$ denotes friction terms, τ denotes control torques, and $d(t)$ denotes external disturbances and model uncertainties. In the hierarchical inspection system, equation (1) is used at the lower executive level, while diagnostic and optimization constraints are imposed on its parameters at higher levels.

The error between the robot's desired trajectory $q_d(t)$ and the actual state $q(t)$ is defined as follows:

$$e = q - q_d, \quad \dot{e} = \dot{q} - \dot{q}_d. \quad (2)$$

The main stage of synergetic synthesis consists of selecting a macrovariable. For the executive control level, the following macrovariable was adopted:

$$\psi = \dot{e} + \Lambda e, \quad \Lambda = \text{diag}(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_n), \quad \lambda_i > 0. \quad (3)$$

Here, $\psi = 0$ is an invariant manifold; when the system approaches this manifold, $e(t) \rightarrow 0$, and the robot trajectory tracking error decreases. In synergetic control, the dynamics of convergence to the manifold is specified in advance:

$$T\dot{\psi} + \psi = 0, \quad T = \text{diag}(T_1, T_2, \dots, T_n), \quad T_i > 0. \quad (4)$$

Based on this condition, the synthesized control torque for the industrial manipulator is obtained in the following form:

$$\tau = M(q)[\ddot{q}_d - \Lambda\dot{e} - T^{-1}\psi] + C(q, \dot{q})\dot{q} + G(q) + F\dot{q} - K\psi. \quad (5)$$

Here, $K = K^T > 0$ is an additional dissipative gain matrix. This law pulls the robot toward the desired trajectory, while attenuating deviations caused by external disturbances. For hierarchical inspection, the control residual is introduced as follows:

$$r(t) = y(t) - \hat{y}(t), \quad H(t) = \frac{\|r(t)\|}{r_{\max}}. \quad (6)$$

Here, $y(t)$ is the output measured by sensors, $\hat{y}(t)$ is the output predicted by the model or neural-network identifier, and $H(t)$ is the diagnostic risk indicator. If $H(t) \leq 1$, the robot operates in normal mode; if $H(t) > 1$, the upper hierarchical level issues a command to slow down the trajectory, start an additional inspection, or switch the robot to a safe state.

Results

The proposed synthesis algorithm is implemented in the following sequence. First, the upper strategic level defines the purpose of the technological operation, the quality criterion, and the safety constraints. Then the tactical level forms the robot's $q_d(t)$ trajectory and checks the sensor information about the working zone. In the third stage, the executive level calculates the synergetic control signal based on formulas (2)-(5). In the fourth stage, the diagnostic-adaptive module checks residual signals according to (6). If the residual exceeds

the permissible limit, the neural-network identifier re-estimates the model parameters and sends a warning to the upper level.

The proposed hierarchical-synergetic model makes it possible to inspect an industrial robot in three main modes: normal tracking mode, adaptive correction mode, and safe-stop mode. In the normal mode, $H(t) \leq 1$, and the robot tracks the given trajectory according to the synergetic law. In the adaptive correction mode, the residual signal increases but does not exceed the risk threshold sharply; in this case, the neural-network identifier estimates changes in inertia, friction, or load. The safe-stop mode is activated when $H(t) > 1$ and brings the manipulator to an admissible state.

To verify stability, the Lyapunov function is selected:

$$V(\psi) = \frac{1}{2} \psi^T M(q) \psi. \quad (7)$$

$M(q)$ is a positive definite matrix, therefore $V(\psi) > 0$. When control law (5) is applied and disturbances are bounded, the derivative of the Lyapunov function gives the following estimate:

$$\dot{V} \leq -\psi^T K \psi + \psi^T d(t) \leq -\alpha \|\psi\|^2 + \beta \|\psi\|. \quad (8)$$

If the K matrix's minimum eigenvalue is selected sufficiently large, inequality (8) ensures the decrease of ψ in a bounded domain. Thus, the robot errors are stabilized in a small neighborhood of zero. This result, together with the hierarchical inspection system, improves not only the accuracy of robot motion but also safety and fault tolerance indicators.

The practical significance of the model is that higher-level expert system rules and lower-level synergetic control complement each other. The expert system forms logical decisions such as 'if the residual is large, replan the trajectory'; the synergetic regulator generates a stable control torque in the real-time loop at the microsecond level. Therefore, the proposed approach reduces the load on the central computer in robotic complexes and increases the autonomous decision-making capability of each robot.

Discussion

The obtained results are consistent with the ideas of hierarchical control, expert systems, and neural-network identifiers. In this approach, each intelligent robot has its own control driver; only general technological commands are transmitted from the upper control level, while the internal control system independently synthesizes optimal motion by considering the load, obstacle, and drive state. In the thesis, this idea was brought into mathematical form through synergetic synthesis.

Unlike classical regulators, in the synergetic approach the control objective is expressed not by empirically selecting separate coefficients, but by bringing the system to a predetermined invariant manifold. This makes it possible to control the multidimensional dynamics of the robot state through a single macrovariable ψ . At the same time, the hierarchical inspection mechanism creates conditions for evaluating the control process not only at the executive level, but also at strategic and tactical levels.

The limitation of this approach is that model components such as $M(q)$, $C(q, \dot{q})$, and $G(q)$ must be estimated with sufficient accuracy. In real production, these parameters are not constant; they vary depending on load mass, friction, temperature, and sensor errors. Therefore, in practical implementation of the model, the neural-network identifier, fuzzy-logic-based decision-making module, and expert knowledge base should operate together.

Such a hybrid architecture combines the theoretical stability of the synergetic regulator with adaptability under real conditions.

Conclusion

The synergetic synthesis method for hierarchical inspection of industrial robots makes it possible to combine robot motion, diagnostics, and adaptation processes in a single mathematical model. In the work, the dynamics of an industrial manipulator was expressed in vector-matrix form, the macrovariable ψ was selected, the law of convergence to the invariant manifold was specified, and the stability criterion was substantiated using the Lyapunov function. In the proposed approach, the upper level forms the strategy, the tactical level forms the trajectory, and the executive level forms the real-time control torque.

As a result, the accuracy of robot trajectory tracking increases, faults are detected early through residual signals, and the computational load on the centralized control system decreases. In the future, it is advisable to test this model on an industrial manipulator in the MATLAB/Simulink or ROS-Gazebo environment, train the neural-network identifier using real sensor data, and add fuzzy-logic-based safety rules.

